

Vibrant Soundbridge Round Window Vibroplasty: Safety, Coupling Efficiency, and Speech Outcome of the Most Common Coupling Modalities

Nicole Knölke^a Susan Busch^{a,b} Thomas Lenarz^{a,b} Hannes Maier^{a,b}^aDepartment of Otorhinolaryngology, German Hearing Center and Institute of Audioneurotechnology (VIANNA), Hannover Medical School, Hannover, Germany; ^bCluster of Excellence “Hearing4all”, Hannover, Germany

Keywords

Vibrant Soundbridge · Coupling efficiency · Round window vibroplasty · Mixed hearing loss · Active middle ear implant

Abstract

Introduction: The floating mass transducer (FMT) of the Vibrant Soundbridge (VSB) is successfully used for reverse stimulation of the round window membrane (RWM) since 2005, enabling the treatment of conductive and mixed hearing loss. The FMT can be placed directly to the RWM or indirectly by using an interposed material such as fascia and Tutopatch, or a coupler, e.g., the round window coupler (RWC), the round window soft (RWS) coupler, or the custom-made Hannover coupler version 2 (HCV2). The aim of the study was to retrospectively evaluate the long-term outcome of the most common VSB round window (RW) coupling modalities in our clinic with regard to (1) safety and preservation of residual hearing, (2) coupling efficiency (C_{eff}), and (3) speech outcome. **Methods:** A total of 111 RW vibroplasties, a surgical procedure including the implantation of the VSB, in 102 ears (95 patients) performed at the Hannover Medical School between 2006 and 2021 were analyzed. Seventy-nine RW vibroplasties in ears with available preoperative bone conduction pure tone average (BC PTA₄) were included in the safety analysis, focusing on adverse events

(AEs). Furthermore, the audiological outcomes were evaluated in 56 ears (52 patients, 4 bilateral implanted) preoperatively, at initial activation (6–8 weeks), 2 years, and 5 years, including BC PTA₄ (at 0.5, 1, 2, 4 kHz), C_{eff} (in situ measurement – BC PTA₄), effective gain (BC PTA₄ – sound field threshold), and monosyllable word recognition score (WRS; Freiburg monosyllable test at 65 dB SPL). **Results:** The safety analysis showed a total mean AE rate of 29.1%. A statistically significant decline over time in BC PTA₄ was found in groups RWS and HCV2 by 7.6 dB and 8.8 dB (paired *t* test, $p = 0.022$ and $p \leq 0.001$, respectively), at 2 years. The WRS improved over time in all groups, resulting in an overall mean score of 81.1% in the range 70.0% to 90.8% at 2 years, with a statistically significant improvement between IA and 2 years and the best mean WRS of 90.8% at 2 years in group HCV2 (paired *t* test, $p \leq 0.001$). While the C_{eff} was stable and below 25 dB at all time points in most groups, it improved statistically significantly in group RWC by a total of 9.9 dB between IA and 5 years to 16.8 dB (paired *t* test, $p \leq 0.001$). **Conclusion:** The RW vibroplasty is a safe surgery, though complex and challenging. All investigated coupling modalities provided effective treatment for conductive and mixed hearing loss. Patients in group RWC and HCV2 tended to perform noticeably better in terms of aided speech understanding and C_{eff} than those in the other groups.

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Introduction

The Vibrant Soundbridge [1] (VSB; MED-EL GmbH, Austria) is an active middle ear implant which provides mechanical stimulation to the auditory ossicles or directly to the cochlear windows by its floating mass transducer (FMT). The VSB was originally developed to treat patients with sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) by coupling the FMT to the incus [1–3], and the procedure was termed incus vibroplasty. In order to extend the application of the VSB to conductive hearing loss (CHL) and mixed hearing loss (MHL), other coupling sites for the FMT such as the oval window [4, 5], stapes head [6–8], or round window (RW) [9] were investigated and successfully implanted, allowing for the rehabilitation of patients with various middle ear or ear canal disorders.

The feasibility of the RW vibroplasty with direct placement of the FMT in front of the RW membrane (RWM) was demonstrated in 2005 by Colletti et al. [9], but patient outcomes showed a high variability [10–13]. Main reasons were considered to be the mismatch in diameter between the FMT and the RWM [14] and the surgically challenging placement of the FMT at the RW, which may prevent sufficient signal transmission between the FMT and RWM. For this reason, the RW niche must be enlarged to fit the FMT, and the bone surrounding the RWM must be reduced to enable the contact between RWM and FMT, while simultaneously avoiding contact between FMT and the bony structures. To overcome these challenges, indirect coupling was introduced in 2006, using interposed materials between the RW membrane and the FMT such as cartilage, fascia [10, 15, 16], or a collagen membrane made from bovine pericardium (Tutopatch; Tutogen Medical GmbH, Germany) [17]. The thickness and shape of the interposed fascia depend solely on the surgeon and bear the risk of atrophy, while Tutopatch has a defined thickness and does not alter. To enable a more stable and standardized coupling with reproducible results, couplers such as the RW coupler (RWC) with a spherical titanium tip [14, 18–20] and the RW soft (RWS) coupler with a conical silicone tip [21, 22] were developed in 2010 and 2014, respectively. Experiments in temporal bones demonstrated that the coupling efficiency (C_{eff}) depends on the static preload [17, 23] with an optimal coupling force in the range of 5–20 mN [19, 21]. Based on these findings, the custom-made devices Hannover coupler version 1 (HCV1) [24, 25] and version 2 [26, 27] (HCV2) were developed. The Hannover coupler is a mechanical cage for the FMT, with a small ball tip in the front. The Hannover coupler version 1, only applied in 2 cases, featured a simple spring at the rear end to provide a static force on the RWM, and the second

version utilizes a more sophisticated s-shaped spring, which includes a visual preload indicator of the force applied (5 mN–20 mN), as well as an anchor to securely support the spring. The aim of the present study was to retrospectively evaluate the long-term outcome of the previously mentioned six most common VSB RW coupling modalities with regard to (1) safety and preservation of residual hearing, (2) C_{eff} , and (3) speech perception.

Material and Methods

The long-safety and audiological outcomes of the VSB RW coupling were analyzed retrospectively in all patients implanted at the Hannover Medical School (MHH) with a VSB FMT placed at the RW between August 2006 and September 2021. All patient data were collected during routine visits.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients with a VSB implanted in at least one ear with the following most common coupling modalities were included in the analysis: the FMT was positioned in the RW niche (1) without material between FMT and round window membrane (RWM) (group *Direct*), (2) with interposed fascia (group *Fascia*), (3) processed collagen membrane made from bovine pericardium (Tutopatch[®], group *Tutopatch*) between the RWM and the FMT, or by using (4) the titanium RWC (group *RWC*), (5) the RWS coupler, or (6) the custom-made device *HCV2*. Patients were excluded from the analyses if the preoperative bone conduction threshold (BC threshold) (up to a maximum of 3 months before surgery) was not available or not valid, because the BC threshold was either (1) outside the measurement limits of the audiometer, (2) masking of the opposite ear was necessary but not possible, or (3) the patient was physically and mentally unable to perform the measurement. For the audiological evaluation, patients were also excluded if a complete postoperative data set consisting of the BC threshold, in situ threshold (vibrograph threshold [V_{thr}]), aided word recognition score (WRS) in quiet, and aided sound field (SF) threshold was not available at all selected time points (see audiological analysis).

Safety Analysis

The safety of implantation was evaluated based on the number of adverse events (AEs) such as complications, revisions, and explantations. Available postoperative AEs up to the end of the data collection in August 2022 were extracted from medical files of each patient. AEs included

complications, revisions, total revisions, and explantations. Events were classified as complications if they did not require revision or explantation, such as HL, pain, vertigo, or wound infections. Complications caused by the magnet strength of the audio processor that had been resolved by reducing the magnet strength were not considered. Revisions included all surgeries with manipulation (relocation) of the implant, the cable, or the FMT. Total revisions were defined as an explantation in combination with the reimplantation of a new VSB in the same surgery, independent of the new coupling modality or site. Total revisions with reimplantation of an implant other than a VSB were counted as an explantation. The AEs were then divided into four categories according to the cause of their occurrence: (1) implant related (implant or cable defects), (2) coupling related (e.g., FMT migration), (3) surgery related (wound healing disorder, infection, HL, or facial palsy), and (4) medical issue unrelated to implantation (cholesteatoma and other ear surgeries, which required revision or explantation).

A total of 111 RW vibroplasties were available for analysis, including seven ears with a total revision and change of coupling modality (see the flowchart in Fig. 1). Overall, 32 RW vibroplasties were excluded from the safety analysis. Twenty-five patients did not have a reliable preoperative BC threshold, 4 patients were implanted with a different type of FMT coupling in the RW niche than investigated here, and 3 patients were not able to perform the tests. Thus, 79 RW vibroplasties, including 4 bilateral implanted patients and 4 patients with two subsequent RW vibroplasties in one ear, which contributed both to the analysis of the respective coupling modality (see Table 2), could be included in the safety analysis.

Demographics, etiology, and previous middle ear surgeries for each group can be found in Table 1. The mean age at implantation was 55.0 ± 15.6 years (mean value \pm standard deviation [MV \pm SD]) in the range of 11–75 years. The mean preoperative BC threshold was 34.7 ± 12.3 dB HL, and the AC threshold 82.1 ± 15.5 dB HL. Reasons for treatment were chronic otitis media ($n = 35$ ears), cholesteatoma ($n = 21$ ears), otosclerosis ($n = 9$ ears), or malformation ($n = 7$ ears). In 3 patients ($n = 3$ ears), the cause was unknown. Due to these preexisting conditions, an average of 2–3 ear surgeries (including revisions) were performed prior to RW vibroplasty. The surgeries included tympanoplasties ($n = 71$ surgeries in 33 ears), subtotal petrosectomies ($n = 65$, 45 ears), radical cavities (canal wall down mastoidectomies, $n = 22$, 17 ears), VSB reimplantations with change of coupling modality ($n = 8$, 5 ears) (see Table 2), and other ear surgeries ($n = 9$, 2 ears).

Audiological Analysis

The audiological performance was evaluated based on the comparison of average BC threshold, C_{eff} , and effective gain (EG) (all across 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 4.0 kHz) as well as aided WRS over time separately for the different coupling modalities. Hearing thresholds were determined using pure-tone measurements (AC, BC) or warble tones (aided SF threshold). The WRS in quiet was measured using the Freiburg monosyllable test at 65 dB SPL. All measurements were performed in a soundproof chamber, with the opposite ear plugged and muffled or masked if needed.

The in situ thresholds were determined directly via the processor during each fitting procedure using the Symfit[®] fitting software. With the in situ threshold and the BC threshold, the C_{eff} was calculated for each patient ($C_{\text{eff}} = V_{\text{thr}} - \text{BC}$). Further, the EG was determined ($\text{EG} = \text{BC} - \text{SF}$).

For the audiological analysis, three postoperative time periods were defined. Short-term data were collected at the time of initial activation (IA) approximately 6 to 8 weeks after implantation. The mid-term data (2 years) were collected 1–3 years after implantation, and the long-term data (5 years) were collected 4–7 years after implantation. If more than one complete data set was available in the defined time span, the data set closest to the 2-year or 5-year appointment was chosen.

As the majority of patients from groups *Direct*, *Fascia*, and *Tutopatch* were implanted before the implementation of the in situ function in the fitting software, the in situ threshold at IA was not available and therefore not considered for these groups. For the groups *RWS* and *HCV2*, only a small number ($n = 3$ each) of long-term data sets (5 years) were available at the end of data collection in August 2022, and no long-term analysis was performed.

Only ears already included in the safety analysis were further considered for the audiological analysis. Due to missing data caused by loss to follow-up ($n = 15$), explantations or total revisions ($n = 4$), or incomplete measurements ($n = 4$), only 56 ears (52 patients) were included in the audiological analysis (Fig. 1). The mid-term data set (2 years) was collected after an average of 2.7 years, and the long-term data set (5 years) was collected after an average of 5.4 years after implantation.

Statistics

The statistical analysis was performed using SigmaPlot 14 (Systat Software Inc.). Data sets were tested for normal distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk test. For comparison of data sets within groups, the paired *t* test was used in case of normal distribution, or else the Wilcoxon signed rank. When comparing data sets between two groups, the

Fig. 1. Flowchart of data selection for safety and audiological analyses before and after application of exclusion criteria. The mean years after implantation of the collected data are given in mean ± SD. HCV1, Hannover coupler version 1.

Welch's *t* test was used in cases of homogeneity of variances; otherwise, the Mann-Whitney rank-sum test was applied. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used for all tests. Frequency-specific results were calculated, but reported as the MV across 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz (PTA₄). MVs are given with the SD throughout the text.

Progressing HL after implantation can eventually result in a threshold exceeding the audiometer limit. To enable further analysis, a best-case estimate was defined as the audiometer limit plus 5 dB. This estimate was applied to six postoperative BC thresholds ($n = 3$, 500 Hz; $n = 3$, 4 kHz) and to three postoperative *in situ* thresholds ($n = 3$ patients; 4 kHz).

Results

Safety Analysis

The safety analysis focused on the investigations of AEs in $n = 79$ RW vibroplasties up to 16 years after implantation (see Table 2). Overall, 23 AEs (29.1%) with 7 complications, 7 revisions, 5 total revisions, and 4 explantations were observed. The most AEs were found in group *Tutopatch* ($n = 8$, 36.4%) and the lowest rates in groups *Direct* and *HCV2* ($n = 1$, 20%; $n = 3$, 20%, respectively). All complications were surgery related and occurred during or shortly after the surgery. Complications included HL, vertigo, wound infection, facial palsy,

Table 1. Demographics, etiology, and known previous surgeries of all ears in the six coupling groups which were included in the safety analysis ($n = 79$)

Coupling	Direct, $n = 5$	Fascia, $n = 6$	Tutopatch, $n = 22$	RWC, $n = 22$	RWS, $n = 9$	HCV2, $n = 15$
Age, years	58.6±12.0	61.2±10.9	49.0±18.1	56.4±15.0	56.0±17.5	57.5±10.0
AC, dB HL	91.0±15.8	88.1±10.2	76.8±15.5	81.8±15.2	79.4±18.3	75.3±18.3
BC, dB HL	35.9±13.2	44.8±12.6	32.1±15.9	35.7±12.1	31.9±9.4	27.8±10.6
Etiology						
COM	2	3	9	11	3	7
Cholesteatoma	2	2	8	7	1	4
Malformation	1	–	3	1	2	–
Otosclerosis	–	1	–	2	3	4
Unknown	–	–	2	1	–	–
Previous surgeries						
Tympanoplasty	2 (2)	5 (2)	12 (8)	23 (10)	10 (4)	19 (7)
Subtotal petrosectomy	4 (3)	4 (4)	15 (13)	21 (15)	5 (3)	16 (7)
CWDM	4 (2)	2 (2)	5 (5)	3 (3)	–	8 (5)
VSB reimplantation	–	–	–	4 (4)	–	4 (1)
Other ear surgeries	6 (1)	–	–	–	–	3 (1)
Unknown	–	–	(2)	(3)	–	–
Surgeries						
Mean	3.2±1.5	2.0±1.5	1.6±1.2	2.5±1.4	1.7±1.4	3.3±3.8
Range	2–6	0–4	0–4	0–6	0–4	1–17

Surgeries are given as number of surgeries (number of ears). Data are given as mean ± SD. COM, chronic otitis media; CWDM, canal wall down mastoidectomy.

and pain at the implant area (coil). Revisions and total revisions occurred on average after 2 years and were mostly coupling related ($n = 5$) or surgery related ($n = 4$). Coupling-related AEs were caused by FMT migration ($n = 3$) or tissue growth ($n = 2$) which reduced the vibratory movement of the FMT. Explantations were medical related ($n = 2$, cholesteatoma) or device related ($n = 2$, implant or cable failure) and occurred after an average of 5.8 years. Four patients were reimplanted with another type of acoustic implant ($n = 3$, BC hearing aid; $n = 1$, Codacs™ [Cochlear Ltd., Sydney, Australia]). No statistically significant differences were observed between the coupling groups concerning the type, cause, or time of occurrence of AEs (Welch's t test, $p > 0.05$).

Audiological Analysis

Residual Hearing

The preoperative BC thresholds (baseline measurement) differed between coupling groups (Fig. 2a; Table 3). Statistically significant differences were found between the group with the largest HL (group *Fascia*, mean bone conduction pure tone average [BC PTA₄] 48.0 ± 11.3 dB HL) and the two groups with the smallest degrees of HL (group *RWS*, mean BC PTA₄

32.2 ± 9.3 dB HL; group *HCV2*, BC PTA₄ 28.0 ± 9.5 dB HL; Welch's t test, $p = 0.019$ and $p = 0.049$, respectively).

The effect of surgery onto residual hearing preservation was tested by comparing the BC PTA₄ before (preop) and after the surgery (IA, 2 years and 5 years). The comparison of BC PTA₄ before the surgery and at the time of first activation (IA) showed a mean HL of more than 5 dB in group *RWS* and group *HCV2*, which increased over time and became significant after 2 years (*RWS* 7.6 dB, *HCV2* 8.8 dB; paired t test, $p = 0.022$ and $p ≤ 0.001$, respectively). The HL of 8.1 dB after 2 years in group *Direct* was not significant (paired t test, $p = 0.587$). The other coupling groups showed no significant change in residual hearing at any time point after the surgery (paired t test, $p > 0.05$).

Coupling Efficiency

The results of the C_{eff} analysis are displayed in Figure 2b and Table 3. The C_{eff} was determined for the groups *Direct*, *Fascia*, and *Tutopatch* after 2 years and 5 years and for the groups *RWS* and *HCV2* at IA and after 2 years. A mean C_{eff} of approximately 25 dB was achieved by most groups at the investigated time points.

Table 2. Overview of postoperative AEs for the different coupling modalities after VSB implantations ($n = 79$)

Coupling modality	Occurrence [years after surgery]	AE	Detail	New modality	Related to
Direct	0.0	Complication	HL		Surgery
Fascia	4.9	Total revision	FMT migration	OWC	Coupling Surgery
	3.0	Total revision	Infection	RWC	
Tutopatch	0.0	Complication	HL		Surgery
	0.0	Complication	Vertigo		Surgery
	0.0	Complication	Wound infection		Surgery
	3.1	Revision	Tissue growths	RWC	Coupling
	2.9	Revision	Cholesteatoma		Medical
	3.5	Total revision	Implant defect	RWC	Device
	0.7	Total revision	Infection	RWC	Surgery
RWC	8.0	Explantation	Implant defect	BB	Device
	0.0	Complication	Facial palsy		Surgery
	0.0	Complication	Wound infection		Surgery
	0.0	Complication	Pain (coil)		Surgery
	0.0	Revision	Late facial palsy		Surgery
	5.8	Explantation	Cable defect	BAHA	Device
	4.0	Explantation	Cholesteatoma	CODACS	Medical
RWS	5.3	Explantation	Cholesteatoma	BB	Medical
	0.3	Revision	FMT migration	HCV1	Coupling Surgery
	0.0	Revision	Infection		
HCV2	1.8	Revision	FMT migration		Coupling
	3.7	Revision	Tissue growths		Coupling
	0.5	Total revision	Dysacusis		Medical

OWC, oval window coupling; HL, hearing loss; HCV1, custom-made device Hannover coupler version 1; BB, Bonebridge (MED-EL).

An exception was found in the *RWC* group at IA (26.7 ± 8.1 dB) and the *Tutopatch* group at the 2 years date (26.6 ± 15.9 dB). The C_{eff} improved significantly in the group *RWC* by 6.1 dB from IA to 2 years (paired t test, $p = 0.035$) and by 3.8 dB from 2 years to 5 years (paired t test, $p = 0.015$). The C_{eff} of the other groups improved by <3.4 dB from IA to 2 years or 2 years to 5 years. In the *Fascia* group, however, a slight but nonsignificant deterioration of C_{eff} by 3.5 dB from 2 years to 5 years was determined. No significant differences were found between coupling groups at any time (Welch's t test, $p > 0.05$).

Effective Gain

The EG was determined as the SF threshold deducted from the BC threshold (see Fig. 2c; Table 3). A positive EG, indicating a closure of the air-bone gap, was determined in the groups *Direct*, *Fascia*, and *HCV2* at IA and additionally in the groups *RWS* and *RWC* at the 2 years date. No significant differences in EG were found between the coupling groups at any time (Welch's t test,

$p > 0.05$). The EG improved in all groups from IA to the 2 years date, but the results were only statistically significant in group *RWC* and group *HCV2* (paired t test, $p = 0.01$; $p = 0.002$, respectively). The EG of the *Fascia* group declined nonsignificantly by 3.2 dB from 2 years to 5 years.

Word Recognition in Quiet

The hearing benefit was evaluated by comparing the aided WRS over time and between coupling groups as shown in Figure 2d and Table 3. At the IA, the mean scores ranged from 50.0% (*Fascia*), 67.5% (*HCV2*), 71.9% (*Tutopatch*), 72.9% (*RWC*), and 73.1% (*RWS*) up to 80.0% (*Direct*). After 2 years, the improvement of WRS compared to the IA ranged from 2.5 percentage points (pp) (*RWS*) to 23.3 pp (*HCV2*), with the latter being statistically significant (*HCV2*, 67.5% vs. 90.8%; paired t test, $p \leq 0.001$). The scores remained constant up to 5 years in the investigated groups (Table 3) with no significant differences between coupling groups (Welch's t test, $p > 0.05$).

Fig. 2. Audiological results from top to bottom. **a** BC PTA₄. **b** C_{eff}. **c** EG. **d** WRS in quiet. Individual data points at each date are given as open circles. Significant differences are indicated above the box plots (paired *t* test) with **p* < 0.05; ***p* < 0.01, and ****p* ≤ 0.001. Solid lines depict the median, dashed lines the mean, and the whiskers 5th/95th percentiles.

Table 3. Results of the audiological analysis

	Date	Direct, <i>n</i> = 4	Fascia, <i>n</i> = 5	Tutopatch, <i>n</i> = 13	RWC, <i>n</i> = 14	RWS, <i>n</i> = 8	HCV2, <i>n</i> = 12
BC [dB HL]	Preop	36.6±14.7	48.0±11.3	31.7±18.4	36.3±12.3	32.2±9.3	28.0±9.5
	IA	39.1±7.9	52.5±8.8	31.2±18.4	34.1±14.8	39.4±7.4	34.0±9.4
	2 yr	44.7±14.6	49.8±8.9	32.6±16.2	37.4±13.8	39.8±8.1	36.8±8.7
	5 yr	44.7±15.9	48.0±7.4	36.0±15.9	38.0±11.9	–	–
<i>C_{eff}</i> [dB]	IA	–	–	–	26.7±8.1	22.3±11.3	20.9±9.4
	2 yr	18.1±1.9	19.3±9.4	26.6±15.9	20.6±7.8	19.5±8.8	20.6±6.7
	5 yr	14.7±2.9	22.8±13.6	24.2±14.6	16.8±5.7	–	–
EG [dB]	IA	5.0±3.2	5.5±15.6	–8.6±16.2	–5.2±11.9	2.5±7.5	–0.3±6.5
	2 yr	9.7±7.6	14.5±7.69	–1.2±17.7	1.5±12.0	6.7±9.2	7.9±8.8
	5 yr	10.9±6.9	11.3±8.4	–0.2±11.5	8.6±12.5	–	–
WRS [%]	IA	80.0±12.3	50.0±23.5	71.9±26.9	72.9±18.6	73.1±19.5	67.5±16.5
	2 yr	87.5±8.3	70.0±23.3	80.0±17.5	82.5±11.8	75.6±24.0	90.8±8.1
	5 yr	87.5±8.3	69.0±29.6	79.6±17.0	80.7±11.0	–	–

Displayed are MVs ± SDs.

Discussion

The current manuscript presents, to the best of our knowledge, the first comprehensive study that compares six different RW vibroplasty coupling modalities regarding safety, speech outcome, and coupling quality (efficiency and stability) for mid-term (2 years) and long-term (5 years) data.

Safety Analysis

For the safety analysis, we examined all AEs after implantation over an average follow-up period of 6.6 ± 4.3 years for 79 patients. We found no statistically significant difference between different coupling modality groups with respect to the quantity or type of AEs.

The overall AE rate was 29.1%, which is in the lower range of vibroplasty AEs reported by other studies. Vickers et al. [28] analyzed a cohort of 163 vibroplasty patients, pooling different coupling sites and couplers and reported an AE rate of 24.5% over 6 years, whereas Zahnert et al. [20] showed 33 AEs in a group of 24 vibroplasties with RWC, oval window coupling, CliP and Bell coupler over 3 years.

A subgroup of the AEs are coupling-related revisions. Revisions were assumed to be coupling related if the WRS dropped suddenly or over time despite stable BC thresholds and changes in V_{thr} were noticed at the same time. The coupling deficit was confirmed by the surgeon during the revision surgery. Our study included five events (6.3%) of coupling-related revisions. In 2 patients (*Tutopatch*, *HCV2*), the FMT was immobilized due to

tissue growth, and in 3 patients (*Fascia*, *RWS*, *HCV2*), a loss of contact between the FMT and RWM was observed.

The number of coupling-related revisions found in other studies varies widely. While Skarzynski et al. [12] showed a rate of 9.5% over 3 years in a group of patients with direct coupling (*n* = 21), Schraven et al. [29] even found a revision rate of 71%, with regard to their subgroup of RW vibroplasty without a coupler (*Direct*, *Fascia*, and *Tutopatch*), while in their group RWC, as in this study, no revision was necessary. The revision rates found in our study and in the literature suggest that the use of the RWC reduces the number of coupling-related revisions.

Another issue is AEs related to recurrent cholesteatoma in patients without subtotal petrosectomy, as shown by Sprinzel et al. [30] with a survival rate of 59.1% within a 6-year observation time. In this study, 20 out of 24 patients with cholesteatoma underwent subtotal petrosectomy at least 6 months prior to VSB implantation, which is a standard procedure in our clinic [31]. Over an average of 6.6 years, the survival rate was 75% in patients without subtotal petrosectomy and 89.5% in patients with subtotal petrosectomy. The two-step procedure presumably reduces the risk of a recurring cholesteatoma.

In addition to the previously reported AEs, we observed three device failures (3.8%) due to a mechanical impact on the implant site (1 patient) and unknown reasons (2 patients), resulting in one total revision and two explantations. Similar rates of device failures of 1.2% [28], 4% [32], and 7% [33] were reported in studies including large cohorts of 92 to 163 patients with multiple

types of vibroplasties. Overall, the risk of device failure is low, and therefore, no correlation could be found associated with a specific coupling modality.

In total, out of the 79 RW vibroplasties analyzed, four explantations were performed after a mean time of use of 5.8 ± 1.5 years. These patients were not reimplanted with a VSB for various unrelated reasons, including progressive HL, medical, and personal reasons.

In addition, general risks of ear surgeries were found in single cases (each rate $<5\%$) in this analysis with a combined AE rate of 13.9%. The risks include vertigo, facial nerve palsy, infections, and HL, which have been reported repeatedly in previous studies [16, 20, 30, 31].

Residual Hearing

Hearing preservation is an equally important aspect in evaluating the safety of ear surgeries. In our study, groups *Fascia*, *Tutopatch*, and *RWC* showed a stable BC threshold even after 5 years. However, groups *Direct*, *RWS*, and *HCV2* showed a mean HL between 7.6 dB and 8.8 dB at 2 years. Although all frequencies were affected, the HL was more pronounced at 4 kHz and 6 kHz. The decline in BC PTA₄ in group *RWS* and *HCV2* was already noticeable at IA (6 dB to 7.2 dB), unlike in group *Direct*, where the decline appeared between IA and 2 years (5.6 dB). Previous studies analyzing groups *Fascia* [16] and *RWC* [20] report a stable BC threshold up to 3.3 years after implantation. In studies including the *RWS*, the mean pre- or postoperative BC PTA₄ was either reported across a mixed patient group including different types of vibroplasties [19, 22], or the preoperative BC threshold [34] or any HL <10 dB was not reported [19].

To identify possible causes of HL, an extended screening of all patients with a HL between 5 dB and 10 dB within the first 2 years was carried out. However, no relationships/correlations were found between the HL of the patients and their demography, etiology, pathology, or number of prior surgeries. Merely, a HL shortly after implantation may suggest that it is surgery related or possibly coupler related.

The *RWS* and *HCV2* have been designed with a small tip diameter to allow deeper placement into the RW niche than previous coupling modalities. The *HCV2*, in particular, was developed to enable application and monitoring of the applied preload. The pressure in the cochlear caused by the preload could also have a potential effect on the BC threshold. Moreover, the *HCV2* is relatively long (6.2 mm) compared to the FMT with *RWC* (3.2 mm) and *RWS* (3.3 mm). This is due to the extended tip and spring, which requires an even larger RW niche than the other

RW coupling types. As Pau et al. [35] stated, noise trauma might be caused by bone removal close to the RWM. There might be an additional risk of noise trauma when enlarging the RW niche on the opposite side of the RWM. Further research is required to evaluate these hypotheses.

Audiological Outcomes

The focus of every treatment with a hearing aid is the rehabilitation of speech understanding, which is achieved with a WRS $\geq 75\%$ following Mueller and Killion [36]. Except for group *Direct*, the score at IA remained below 75% in all groups and improved over time, resulting in a WRS $\geq 75\%$ in all groups except group *Fascia*. The improvement over time can be explained by optimized fitting performed during clinical visits, habituation effects, as well as improving C_{eff} . From 2 years on, the WRS of all groups remained stable up to the 5-year appointment. As noted by Müller et al. [34], patients, who have received inadequate or no treatment for a long time prior to implantation, are often sensitive to loudness and refuse appropriate amplification. We observed only 3 patients (*Tutopatch* $n = 1$, *RWS* $n = 2$) with documented sensitivity to loudness who did not accept an optimized fitting even after years, and failed to improve speech reception (WRS $\leq 50\%$). However, most patients could adapt to amplification over a few fittings (habituation effect). This effect was particularly noticeable in group *HCV2*, in which 6 patients were initially sensitive to loudness. With increased amplification, some patients improved by up to 55 pp in WRS at 2 years, resulting in a statistically significant improvement in group *HCV2*. In group *HCV2*, the WRS improved statistically significant over time from IA to the best mean WRS of $90.8\% \pm 8.1\%$ at 2 years. Groups *Direct* and *RWC* showed a WRS with low SDs at 2 years of $87.5\% \pm 8.3\%$ and $82.5\% \pm 11.8\%$, respectively, suggesting reproducibility of audiological results. In comparison, Zahnert et al. [20] found a slightly lower mean WRS of $72.2\% \pm 15.6\%$ after 3 years in a group of 9 patients with *RWC*. Larger variations can be found at 2 years in groups *Fascia*, *Tutopatch*, and *RWS*, with a mean WRS of $70.0\% \pm 23.3\%$, $80.0\% \pm 17.5\%$, and $75.6\% \pm 24.0\%$, respectively. Böheim et al. [16] reported an even lower mean WRS of $65\% \pm 30\%$ after 3.3 years in a group *Fascia* including 12 patients. In regard to group *RWS*, varying results were reported, ranging from $53.8\% \pm 18.2\%$ [37] to $78.1\% \pm 15.1\%$ [34], indicating a certain unpredictability.

In clinical routine, we observed a ceiling effect of the aided SF threshold at approximately 25 dB HL. Nevertheless, an average speech recognition score $\geq 80\%$ was provided. One possible cause is the limitation of the SF

threshold by the intrinsic microphone noise at approximately 20 dB HL. In case of patients with a BC threshold approximately <20 dB, the noise is audible and masks softer sounds, thus limiting the aided SF threshold. This effect can result in a negative EG giving the false impression of insufficient amplification.

In order to compare the groups, it would be required to divide them into subgroups according to their BC PTA₄. For simplicity, we focused on changes in average EG over time. An overclosure of the air-bone gap (positive EG) was achieved at IA in groups *Direct*, *Fascia*, and *RWS*. Similar to speech recognition, the EG improved in all groups over time, with statistically significant improvements for both the *RWC* and *HCV2* groups between IA and 2 years, resulting in a positive EG in all groups except group *Tutopatch* at 2 years.

The C_{eff} is a parameter evaluating the transfer function between an AMEI and the inner ear. The V_{thr} measurement via the Symfit[®] software was developed by MED-EL based on the classical incus coupling [34, 38]. Thus, the C_{eff} indicates whether other types of vibroplasties are better or worse than the classical incus coupling. However, as a relative measure it is suitable for the comparison of different coupling modalities between groups and in the same type of vibroplasty, as shown in this study.

The lowest C_{eff} was found in group *Direct* (18.1 dB at 2 years, 14.7 dB at 5 years), although with only 4 patients, results should be interpreted carefully. Atturo et al. [39] demonstrated that the RW has a unique shape and size in each patient, and its diameter might be smaller than one of the FMT (1.5 mm). In case of direct coupling, contact may occur between the FMT and the bone surrounding the RW, resulting in a coupling deficit [40]. We have no information on the shape of the RWs of the implanted patients, but it can be assumed that the patients in group *Direct* had a RW diameter ≥ 1.5 mm to place the FMT. The risk of diameter mismatch and the resulting challenges were the reasons for the adoption of indirect coupling, initially with fascia or *Tutopatch* and later with a coupler.

Even though the mean C_{eff} remained stable in group *Fascia*, we see some patients with a deterioration in the C_{eff} , which could indicate that fascia is degraded by the body [41, 42]. This assumption is supported by the observations made during one of the two reported total revisions in group *Fascia*. In this case of FMT migration after 4.9 years, no fascia was found in front of the RW during surgery. The *Tutopatch* group showed the worst mean C_{eff} with 26.6 dB \pm 15.9 dB after 2 years and the largest variability among the groups. One possible reason

might be that *Tutopatch* is placed directly in front of the membrane prior to FMT placement, which might hinder visual feedback and hence optimization of the contact during positioning.

Couplers have been developed to optimize the C_{eff} and, in particular, to reduce its variability. While in all other coupler groups the C_{eff} can be assumed to be stable, group *RWC* showed a mean C_{eff} of 26.7 dB \pm 8.1 dB at IA, but decreased statistically significant at both 2 years and 5 years to 16.8 dB \pm 5.7 dB, suggesting an improved transfer. We assume that the spherical shape of the *RWC* centers the coupler in the RWM, leading to an optimized coupling. While the C_{eff} in group *RWS* with 19.5 dB \pm 8.8 dB at 2 years was comparable to the other investigated coupler groups, the mean WRS with 75.6% \pm 24.0% at 2 years was inferior to most other modalities with a high variability between patients. A comparable WRS of 78.1% \pm 15.1% was reported in Müller et al. [34], but simultaneously they reported a lower (better) C_{eff} of 12.7 dB \pm 11.0 dB. This leads to the assumption of a floor effect, where a lower efficiency no longer provides additional benefits as suggested by Müller et al. [19]. The smallest variations and minor changes in C_{eff} were observed in group *HCV2*, indicating that the coupler remains in position regardless of alterations in the tissue or bone surrounding the RW.

We recommend a stringent documentation and evaluation of surgical boundary conditions in RW vibroplasty to enable identification of contributing factors, such as anatomical features of the RW, preexisting or due to previous surgeries and drilling-related characteristics such as speed, duration, and depth. This may help identify reasons for differences in results, particularly in relation to residual hearing.

Conclusion

This is the first comprehensive study comparing the most common different RW vibroplasties in terms of safety, residual hearing, and audiological outcomes. Although RW vibroplasty is a complex and challenging ear surgery, it is not associated with a higher risk than other vibroplasties or comparable complex ear procedures.

All investigated coupling modalities ensured a successful treatment benefit for conductive HL and mixed HL, providing rehabilitation of speech recognition. Moreover, a comparison between the groups showed that patients with *RWC* and *HCV2* couplers tended to perform noticeably better in terms of aided speech understanding and C_{eff} than those in the other groups.

Statement of Ethics

All patient data were collected during routine visits, and processing was anonymized in accordance with regulation (EU) 2016/679 of April 27, 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data. The study was approved by the local Ethics Committee (Hannover Medical School, Approval No. 1897–2013) and is in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent for anonymous use of data was obtained at the admission of patients.

Conflict of Interest Statement

All authors received travel support by MED-EL to conferences. The authors disclose no other conflicts of interest.

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Author Contributions

N.K.: writing – original draft, conceptualization, visualization, methodology, investigation, and formal analysis. S.B.: writing – review and editing, methodology, and supervision. T.L.: writing – review and editing, and resources. H.M.: writing – review and editing, conceptualization, methodology, supervision, and resources. All authors discussed the results and implications of this study.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the study's results are not publicly available as it could compromise the privacy of research participants but are available from the corresponding author (N.K.) upon reasonable request.

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